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SIGNIFICANCE OF "COACHING" METHODOLOGY

Annotation: this article describes the possibility of developing a student's individuality with the help of coaching methodology (such as cognition, awareness, responsibility), a special form of knowledge, creative partnership of two personalities who rely on the student's desire to create their personal and professional life, teaching them to think and comprehend in a new way.

Аннотация: ушбу мақолада коучинг методикаси орқали талабанинг индивидуаллигини ривожлантириш (билиш, англаш, жавобгарлик кабилар), билим беришнинг ўзгача шакли, талабанинг шахсий ва касбий ҳаётини яратиш истагига таянган иккита шахснинг ижодий шериклиги, янгича ўйлаш ва фикрлашга ўргатиш каби имкониятлари мавжудлиги ҳақида фикрлар баён этилган.

Аннотация: в этой статье излагается возможность развития индивидуальности студента с помощью методологии коучинга (такой как познание, осознанность, ответственность), особой формы знания, творческого партнерства двух личностей, которые полагаются на желание студента создавать свою личную и профессиональную жизнь, обучая их думать и осмысливать по-новому.

Key words: coaching methodology, student's individuality, knowledge, awareness, a special form of knowledge transfer, creative partnership, new thinking

Калит сўзлар: коучинг методикаси, талабанинг индивидуаллиги, билиш, англаш, билим беришнинг ўзгача шакли, ижодий шериклик, янгича фикрлаш

Ключевые слова: методология коучинга, индивидуальность студента, знания, осведомленность, особая форма передачи знаний, творческое партнерство, новое мышление

In the education of our republic, researches are being conducted on the issues of improving the educational system based on innovative technologies, strengthening its national ground, raising the training of socially active, competitive personnel to the level of world standards. Quality changes and high efficiency in the field of education depend on their compatibility with the world educational requirements, the achievement of positive results in professional training of students in our country, first of all, on the extent to which their acquired competencies are put into practice. For this purpose, we researched the use of the "Coaching" methodology.

"Coaching" methodology determines the goal and optimal ways to achieve it; increases student independence and responsibility; to be satisfied with one's work; finding new ways of effective cooperation; quickly find an important solution in difficult situations;

alignment of individual goals with the goals of the educational institution; enrich your lifestyle; open new opportunities; enrich life with new productive personal relationships and help others.

Coaching means "to train" in English. In education, it refers to a continuous process that creates an opportunity for the effective activity of the teacher and the student.

Coaching is providing individual consultation to a student to achieve an important educational goal, unlocking his inner potential, forming and developing the necessary abilities and skills, and mastering advanced strategies for achieving results. The purpose of coaching is not to teach something, but to create conditions for self-education so that the student acquires the necessary knowledge and experience.

This methodology is designed to understand the tasks and needs of students for their professional and personal growth, and to expand their opportunities. It is focused on the implementation of plans in various areas of life, such as education, business, interpersonal relationships, family, and physical fitness.

Another major goal of coaching is to teach students how to think and think in new ways. First, it is necessary to establish a relationship of trust.

With the use of coaching, students achieve their goals very quickly, in the most efficient way and with satisfaction. The advantages of coaching are that it improves the effectiveness of educational activities, develops students in all aspects and teaches them in the best ways and methods.

Coaching involves rapid learning, which in turn: brings joy and satisfaction; the interaction in the team improves; the quality of life and learning environment improves; the teacher will have a lot of free time; many creative ideas appear; human resources and skills are used well; unlocks the previously undiscovered talent of students, etc.

Thus, coaching is a creative partnership of two people based on the desire to develop the student's individuality (knowledge, awareness, responsibility, etc.), a special form of education, and the desire to create a student's personal and professional life. This is certainly important in the formation of students' learning competencies. That is why it is important for teachers to study it thoroughly and introduce it into the educational process as a new method entering the educational system.

It is desirable to form learning-cognitive competences in the coaching methodology offered by us based on the MIMM structure: M-motivation, I-information, M-methodology, M-coordination stages, students' interest in learning and understanding is directed to independent activities.

The main factor in the formation of educational competences is the participation of students in creative research, activation of independent work, for this it is preferable to use interesting tasks that train and develop thinking.

Students are guided to independent work based on increasing their motivation to learn. Today's students should be educated in a non-standard manner, leaving a little aside from traditional education. Today is the age of technology and information. It is the need of the hour to educate a student with the ability to think independently and creatively, who can compete.

Coaching, MIMM, reverse learning methods create initiative in solving spontaneous problems in students. These methods form students' modern social skills, such as independent work, logical and creative thinking, designing, self-analysis, showing talent, and applying the acquired knowledge in life.

In the formation of internal motivation of students in higher education, it is necessary to create such conditions for the teacher, in which the social importance of the basis of theoretical preparation, activity (educational-management, educational-informational, educational-logical) is explained. For example, using business games, implementing projects, etc.

Forecasting and planning: the preliminary analysis of problematic situations allows to determine the sequence of activity stages, to choose the necessary tools for its implementation, to understand the nature of the problems, to make the necessary changes, to forecast the expected results.

Classification of concepts, their classification, concretization, and practical application are carried out. Students' activities are organized according to the principles "from abstract to concrete" and "from general to specific".

The final-reflexive stage: the results of problem solving are analyzed, corrections are made, mistakes are worked on. The main role refers to the adequate self-assessment of students, which testifies to the student's readiness for self-development, self-education.

It is worth saying that this type of activity allows reflection of personal self-development, emerges as both internal and external mechanisms of self-organization, and provides an opportunity to predict the development of the further interaction of subjects during the implementation of the project in the independent work process.

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